

Evolution of Chaityas and Shrines Excavated at Udayagiri, District-Jajpur, Odisha, India -A Stratigraphical Analysis

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Abstract

Attempt has been made through the paper to study development of Buddhist shrines in India from the 6th century B.C. to about the 11th century A.D. in general and Udaygiri archaeological site in particular to show that the Buddhists adopted different types of building plans like elliptical, circular, apsidal and quadrilateral in different periods based on the ideological background of the particular period. In the present context of archaeological research, it is very difficult to reconstruct any clear picture of ideological background of *chaitya-grihas* or Buddhist shrines since the archaeological remains supported by epigraphical evidences of successive phases of construction do not give any clear picture of the original structure belonging to a particular period. As no earlier attempt was made in any of previous excavations to correlate the structural remains with the stratigraphic data, all important evidences relating to the development of Buddhist shrines in many sites are now lost. But Udaygiri site gives us ample evidences to relate the architectural style of buildings of the shrine with the Buddhist philosophy prevalent in the particular period.

Key Words: Buddhist Philosophy , Buddhist Architecture , Chaityagriha, Architectural change

Introduction

This paper presents a few studies in the development of Buddhist shrine in India from the 6th century B.C. to about the 11th century A.D. Firstly, a humble attempt has been made to show that

the Buddhists adopted different types of building plans like elliptical, circular, apsidal and quadrilateral in different periods based on the ideological background of the particular period. In the present context of archaeological research, it is very difficult to reconstruct any clear picture of ideological background of *chaitya-grihas* or Buddhist shrines since the archaeological remains supported by epigraphical evidences of successive phases of construction do not give any clear picture of the original structure belonging to a particular period. As no earlier attempt was made in any of previous excavations to correlate the structural remains with the stratigraphic data, all important evidences relating to the development of Buddhist shrines in any sites are now lost. In this context we will discuss about the evolution of architectural forms of the Buddhist shrines at Udaygiri archaeological site Odisha on the basis of ideological changes.

Different architectural forms of Buddhist shrines throughout India

Majority of the sites like Rajgir, Gopika cave, Sravasti and Kausambi are confined to the Gangetic basin which is the cradle of elliptical type of architectural plan. Except the Gopika cave in the Nagarjuni Hill all others are attributed to the Buddhists. But the elliptical shrines of Besnagar and Nagari, both being in central India, are belonged to the Vaishnava sect. The earliest elliptical structure of Jivak Amravana monastery located at Rajgir, may be dated to *circa* 6th-5th century B.C. (Ghosh,1950). It is interesting to record here that neither any stupa nor any shrine seems to have existed at Rajgir. Next, the Gopika or Nagarjuni cave (fig-1) in the Nagarjuni hill, District- Gaya, Bihar, ascribable to the 3rd century B.C., consists mainly of a single hall and entered by a passage in the middle (Cunningham,1875). During Asokan regime several architectural forms like stupas, monasteries, rock-cut caves, free standing pillars, minor or major rock-edicts, stepped well etc owed much of their popularity throughout the length and breadth of his empire. The *chaitya-grihas* or Buddhist shrines possibly made their first appearance during Asoka's time. Circular and apsidal forms of shrines represent a further stage in the development not only in architecture but also in the sphere of ideology related to *chaitya-griha* or the memorial aspects of the *chaitya*. The concept of shrine was inseparably connected with the subsequently emerged ideas of *Bhakti* and worship. So far as the archaeological remains are concerned these Buddhist shrines conform mainly to three different shapes, viz. (1) circular, (2) apsidal, (3) quadrilateral. It is, however, not certain whether elliptical form was ever connected with the stupa-shrines or not. Elliptical structures of in ancient India are not widely known but these structures corresponding to a linear plan with semi-circular end (Bhandarkar,1920) did exist, which appears to be older than the circular and apsidal ones.

Present study on Udaygiri Archaeological site

The present study involves the large scale excavations at Udayagiri, District- Jajpur, Odisha, during 1985-1989 and 1997-2003, conducted by the Archaeological Survey of India, which explicitly show the doctrinal changes in the largest monastic establishment. Udayagiri brought to light two simultaneous sectarian development of monastic establishments of “*Sri-Madhavapur mahavihara-aryabhikshu-sanghasya*” (Joshi,1992) and “*Sri-Simhaprastha-mahavihara-aryabhiksu-sanghasya*” (Bandopadhyay, 2000)

It is to mention here that within an enclosure wall three types of *chaitya-griha* i.e. circular, apsidal and rectangular dimensions have been unearthed stratigraphically in succession at Udayagiri-2. Perhaps this is the only Buddhist site where we can date and study the evolution of *chaitya-grihas* stratigraphically. This type of evidence has proved that Udayagiri was a most important center of Buddhism. It appears that whenever any change took place in Buddhist philosophy and religion like Hinyana, Mahajana, Bajrajana etc , it 9th change) has been reflected in art and architecture of Udayagiri. For example the original central stone stupa of circular *chaitya-griha* on stone platform has been transplanted in stone apsidal and later on also used in rectangular *chaitya-griha*. Besides, *chaitya-grihas* are encountered in other sites like Lalitagiri, Sisupalgarh and Khandagiri-Udayagiri in Odisha. The architectural development and dating of apsidal *chaitya* Udayagiri was not possible until and unless the comparative study and conclusions are derived from other sites. Further, it is not certain as to how the innovative ideas and concepts were introduced in the construction of apsidal shrine i.e. ritualistic place of worship related to Buddhism. This entails a deep study indeed.

Udayagiri (Lat. 20° 39' N. Long. 86°16' E.) (fig. 2) lies in tehsil Darapana of district Jajpur in Odisha. Situated on the right bank of river Birupa, a branch of Mahanadi, it is 88 km away from Bhubaneswar via Chandikhol on the way to Ratnagiri, in the picturesque valley surrounded by Assia hill on the west, south and north and opened in the east to the bank of river Birupa. The horseshoe shaped valley is vertically divided in to two halves by a ridge. The northern half of the valley named as Udayagiri-1 and Southern half of the valley is known as Udayagiri-2.

Excavation of Udayagiri-2 (1997-2003) revealed one impressive brick-built double storied monastery having its sanctum provided with an ambulatory passage, shrine complex, tank, a large stone platform with a circular *chaitya* facing north in centre, a brick-built rectangular *chaitya-griha* raised over an earlier apsidal stone *chaitya-griha* and other brick and stone stupas within an enclosure wall, stone path way, drain etc. Its stratigraphical level could not be properly established due to iconoclastic and vandalistic activities which took place during 11th century A.D. at the site. On the basis of findings of the apsidal *chaitya-griha* and an inscribed relic container belonging to circa 1st century A.D., and number of sealings and imageries bearing the Buddhist creed the *chaitya-griha* is assignable to the 7th to 9th century A.D. A rock-cut stepped well inscribed with a record shall be ascribed to circa 9th – 10th century .A typical pottery assemblage is also there. From above facts and documents it can be said that the site was under

occupation right from the beginning of the 1st century A.D. to the 13th century A.D. (Shrivastava,2008) However the date of the site could also be pushed back to the 3rd century B.C. on the basis of stratified material remains of the *chaitya-griha* area. The phase wise detailing of the architecture vis a vis the contemporary Buddhist doctrine is discussed below (tabulated form in Appendix 1) :

Circular *chaitya-griha* on masonry platform facing north (phase- I):3rd/2nd century B.C. to 1st century B.C.

The roughly square 14.05m (N-S) and 13.35m (E-W) stone platform (Pl.I) made of seven courses ashlar masonry was approached through a flight of stone steps devised with a *chandrasila* to the north. On the centre of this platform was raised a stone stupa (dia. 3m) traceable only on plan and provided with a circumambulatory path (width 1.22m) demarcated by a low height brick wall from the paved stone platform path (Pl. II). Stratigraphically this is the earliest structural activity of the site below the apsidal masonry *chaitya-griha*. When compared to circular *chaitya* of Bairat (Sahni,nd) Rajasthan or Junar⁸(Fergusson & Burgess 1880) rock-cut circular *chaitya* in Maharashtra this structure could be pushed back to as early as Sunga ascendancy datable to circa 3rd/2nd century B.C. This so called structure could be used as circular *chaitya-griha* during Hinayana period.

The same contemporaneous evidences are also encountered at Lalitagiri below the apsidal *chaitya* and at Sisupalgarh below the recently partially exposed *chaitya* at *Solokhamba* area by the Deccan collage Pune and Cotsen Institute of Archaeology and Department of Anthropology, university of California, los Angeles. The ten donatory inscriptions in shell characters engraved on the platform as well as on its threshold had been the handiwork of later period (7th / 8th century A.D.). Some of the stone slabs used for the pathway of this structure were also inscribed in the same shell script character. The date of this phase may be tentatively fixed between 3rd century B.C. to 1st century B.C. .

Masonry apsidal *chaitya-griha* facing east, 1st century B.C.E to 3rd/4th Century A.D. (phase-II)

The apsidal *chaitya-griha* (23.60m X 15.85m) made of stones enshrining the same stupa (3m) was standing on the earlier stone paved platform. The masonry platform made of finely dressed stones is originally plastered with lime. Presently, the stupa has preserved its *medhi* portion only (Pl. III). Now the facing of the *chaitya* was towards east approached through seven steps of ashlar stone masonry (Pl. IV). On the basis of comparative study of the apsidal *rock-cut chaityas* of Bhaja, Karle, Ajanta and Ellora etc. (Fergusson & Burgess,1880) in Maharashtra, apsidal structural *chaityas* of Sanchi,(Marshall et al ,nd) Sirkap (Marshall,1957)and Saranath (Annual Report 14-15,1920) from 3rd century B.C. (structural temple, Sanchi-40) to 5th century A.D.

(Ajanta cave - 19) then, the present example could be dated between *circa* 1st century B.C. and 3rd century A.D.

Besides, the apsidal *stupa-shrine* at Udayagiri (Ghosh,1993), appears to be datable to *circa* 1st century B.C. earliest. However it is identified as a Jaina temple. But on personal examination it was observed that some elliptical impression on plan (Pl. V) of this structure could also be traced.

During this time, emergence of Mahayanism coincided with introduction of the images of Buddha in the Buddhist art. The new school which sprang up in Gandhara and Mathura at the same time in the 1st century A.D. defied the Hinayana school and gradually the image of the Buddha began to adorn all subsequent Buddhist sites in India and outside. But due to lack of Buddha image of Mahayana periods from the sites indicate that at Udayagiri-2, Hinayana phase might have continued for a longer period, from 1st century B.C. to 3rd/4th century A.D. But at Lalitagiri in Cuttack district, Langudi in Jajpur district and Ganiapalli in Baragarh district few sculptures of Buddha belonging to Mahayana phase are noticed.

Earlier it was thought that, this type of *griha-stupa* neither spread to the east coast nor to the entire Ganga- Yamuna doab. Further, this form however, had its later extension at Bagh , (Marshall,1997), Dhamnar (Fergusson & Burgess,1880) both being in central India. Hence its occurrence at Udaygiri-2, Odisha on the apsidal *chaitya-griha* is the important discovery in the archaeological field. Again, the constricted inner side of the rear western projection (*ratha*) was perhaps meant for accommodating a cult image. But no image is recovered from here which is possibly due to mindless vandalism and rubbing activities at sites. The mouldings akin to the typical contemporary Odishan shrines viz., *khura*, plain recess, *kumbha* and *pata* save for its northern side which was subsequently renovated, the southern and western projections (*rathas*) were decorated with *tulapithas* showing six squares cut with lotus petals, a feature found in early type of temples of 7th -8th century A.D. Shrivastava,2008) It also differs from the western Indian series in having quadrangular stupa shrine within the monastic enclosures. So from where this conception was derived that has to be finalized with dates.

Rectangular brick *chaitya-griha* facing east, 4th century A.D. to 7th century A.D. (phase-III)

With the doctrinal changes, the earlier constructed apsidal *chaitya-griha* might have come in to disuse. Later on, a brick-built rectangular *chaitya-griha* with its *triratha* shrine was erected over the already existing apsidal platform, retaining the same stupa but with east orientation (Pl. VI). The date of this phase may be tentatively fixed between 4th century A.D. to 7th century A.D. At the same time, the early distribution of such type of *chaitya* in the western coast Buddhist *rock-cut* sites like Kuda, Mahad, Karad ,(Burgess,1883) , Sailarwadi, Junnar, Kanheri etc (Fergusson & Burgess,1880) and in the Taxila region have made their appearance during the 1st century A.D. to 4th century A.D.

(d) Rectangular brick *chaitya-griha* with an entrance orienting north, 7th century A. D. to 9th Century . A.D. (phase - IV)

The rectangular brick built *chaitya-griha* was entered through an ornate doorway from north which has now been completely destroyed. Only stone foundation of that doorway was unearthed *in situ* position. The southern arm of *chaitya-griha* was utilised to act as a low stone platform consisting of eight lions (originally they were ten as evidenced by space and their pieces) which served as *Simhasana* (Pl. VII) for installing five colossal images of *Dhyani*-Buddha displaying with usual postures as suggested by large fragmentary sculptural members recovered from the adjacent area. Besides, Fragmentary images of Buddhist deity, *naga-dwarapalas* and pieces carved with scenes of day to day life were also recovered. During this time possibly so called “*Simhaprastha Mahavihara*” was transformed from *Mahayana* to *Vajrayana* sectarian affiliation.

On the cardinal directions the *chaitya* shrine was provided with *gavakshas* of decorated stone *jails* worked with three-hooded snake motif.

The brick apsidal platform was also in use as evidenced by projection towards north. During this period the donatory inscription in shell characters on the stone platform as well as its threshold were possibly engraved. This phase can be placed from *circa* 7th century A.D. to 9th century A.D. tentatively. After that “*Madhavapura Mahavihara*” was probably established separately by queens of Bhaumakaras for nuns to practice *Kalachakratantra*.

(e) Rectangular shrine complex facing east, 9th century. A.D. to 11th Century A.D. (Phase-V)

In Udayagiri-2, at north-west outer corner area of the monastery, the shrine complex (Pl. VIII) within an enclosure has its entrance (3.04m wide) towards the east exposed away from the *chaitya-griha* area. A massive image of Avalokitesvara lying on its back dominated over the surrounding, attesting the importance of the area.

To enshrine the presiding deities, some shrine chambers were constructed on the northern and southern wings of the structure. Remains of two externally projected chambers on the southern side measuring- the south western one 1.56m in width while the length is obscured and the southeastern one being 1x 1.30m respectively. Traces of two externally projected shrine-chambers were found on the northern side measuring the northwestern 1.50 sq.m. while the eastern one 1.50 x 2.05m which are better retained with its door-seal and stone pedestal for enshrining the deity. On the northwestern corner is preserved an externally projected shrine-chamber 1.84x1.32m. This cell along with the \uparrow raised base for accommodating an image which fits well with the size of the Avalokitesvara image and it can be inferred that the raised altar might have enshrined the deity of Avalokitesvara.

In the Buddhist pantheon, Avalokitesvara is the most popular of the Buddhist Bodhisattvas. The Tibetan work *Mani Kambum* relates the story of his birth. Once upon a time, Amitabha, after giving himself up to earnest meditation caused a white ray of light to issue emerge from his right eye, which brought Padmapani (Avalokitesvara) Bodhisattva into existence. Amitabha blessed him, where upon the Bodhisattva brought forth the prayer; Om Mani Padme Hum, Oh! The jewel (of creation) is in the lotus!

Avalokitesvara is thus the spiritual son of *Dhyani* Buddha Amitabha and his Saktipandara. Along with them he presides over the present kalpa which is the *Bhadra kalpa*. He is to rule over the universe during the period between the *Mahaparinirvana* of the *Manushi* Buddha Gautama and the appearance of the future Buddha, Maitreya. Five thousand years after the Gautam Buddha, Maitreya will appear as a *Manushi* Buddha in the fifth world, which will be created by Visvapani (fifth *Dhyani Bodhisattva*). That is one reason for his popularity. The *Gunakarandavyuha* (a fourth century text) relates how he refuses Nirvana, until all human beings are in possession of the Buddhi knowledge. He assumes protean manifestations of divinity. The text mentions him as the first god to emerge out of the primordial Buddha (Adi-Buddha) who creates the universe.

The conception of Avalokitesvara is datable to the Asokan period. In the work *Mahavastu*, *Avadana*, the Mahasanghika he is described as the Bhagvan who takes the form of a Bodhisattva, whose duty is to look around (Avalokita) for the sake of instructing the people and for their constant welfare and happiness. This conception of the Bodhisattva Avalokita took concrete form in the *Amitayus Sutra* or the *Sukhavati Vyuha*, a work datable to A.D. 100. The *Guna Karanda vyuha* narrates the story of the creation of the fourth world by Padmapani (a form of Avalokitesvara). 'From between his (Padmapani's) shoulders sprang Brahma; from his two eyes, the Sun and the Moon; from his mouth the air; from his teeth, Sarasvati; from his naval, water; from the roofs of his hair, the Indras and the devatas.'

Avalokitesvara, being the compassionate Bodhisattva, takes humorous forms to lead people to Nirvana. A Buddhist legend refers to his 333 incarnations. He manifests himself repeatedly for the purpose of saving mankind. His worship became popular in Northern India in the 3rd century A.D. and by the 7th century A.D. He became the most popular of the Bodhisattvas. Fa-hien and Yuan Chwang spoke of him with great reverence. The *Sadhanamala* describes fifteen different varieties of Avalokitesvara, in thirty-eight sadhanas (descriptive hymns). But these by no means exhaust all his forms. In the Macchandar Vahal of Kathamandu (Nepal), 108 different forms of him are painted.

The white Tara is regarded as the consort of Avalokitesvara. Tara holds a position of considerable eminence in the Buddhist pantheon. She is a savior Goddess, a deliveress. She is the sakti of Avalokitesvara as Uma is that of Mahesvara. In the Tantrayana, Sakti assumed great importance. The male god was to be approached through his Sakti.(Gupte,1980)

The walls of the complex exhibit beautiful mouldings and traces of 44 carved niches are also visible on the southern and western walls at regular intervals for holding images. The courtyard of the shrine has yielded some vestiges of the flag-stones with which it was paved. The votive stupas were found mostly dislodged from their original position but an assemblage of them over the pavement in the north-west corner of the courtyard is significant. A good number of mutilated images of Bodhisattvas have also been retrieved. The verandah is in a slightly raised level from the courtyard, veneered by slanting bricks. Evidently stone pillars held the roof between the corridor and sanctum cells as well as carved niches were also unearthed. Five such square stone bases are noticed on the verandah. Stones in the drain running almost parallel to the eastern outer wall of shrine complex represent mostly re-used architectural members. Therefore, this appears to be a later accretion. On the basis of a study of the antiquities of the shrine area which includes inscribed images, stones and other objects, it appears that the shrine complex was constructed after rectangular *chaitya* i.e. between c. 9th to 11th century A.D. (Bandopadhyay, 2000).

(f) Post- Buddhist scenario , 12th century. A.D. to 13th century A.D. (phase-VI):

Probably during 12th century A.D. the iconoclastic vandalistic activities in a massive scale destroyed the whole complex. Prior to that, earlier the vaulted windows (Pl. IX) those were provided for free air and light to monastery, closed from both the sides, probably to thwart external threats.

The ornate doorway of rectangular *chaitya* orienting north had been destroyed completely. Fragmentary images of Buddhist deity, naga-dvarapalas, pieces of facade of gateway and pieces of five *Dhyani* Buddhas (Pl. X) were collected from the debris of rectangular *chaitya-griha* complex. All the important stupas were also destroyed with other different forms of Avalokitesvara and images of Bodhisattvas.

The area on the eastern side of the monastery, where the deposits have formed a sudden slope on the edge was thoroughly probed. From the lower level was found the haphazardly laid detached architectural members of a Buddhist temple in stone nearby. Some of these architectural members are akin to temple mouldings and some of them are ornamental in nature containing sculptural representations of semi-divine and divine beings. In the same area were found remains of a masonry structure measuring 7.25x5.90 m. with a 1.05m. thick partition wall (Pl. XI).

The stratigraphical sequence is not possible here due to dump and pits of old materials. This seems to be from some Buddhist temples which might have been thoroughly devastated later on. Though an effort was made later on during close of 12th century A.D. to construct some shrine but could not survive. (Bandopadhyay, 2000)

Excavations of Udayagiri-1 (1985-89) yielded a magnificent monastery and an impressive brick stupa with four *Dhyani* Buddhas viz. Akshobhya (E), Rthasambhava (S), Amitabha (W) and

Amoghasidhi (N) in niches at the middle of four cardinal directions. The important finds included terracotta seals and sealings with the inscription “SriMadhavapu rmahavihara-arya-bhikshu-sanghasha” proving that the monastery at Udayagiri-1 was widely known as *Madhavapur Mahavihara* then. On the basis of findings the site may be dated to 8th to 13th century A.D. Due to the evidence of an enclosure wall in front of the monastery in all the four phases and fragments of faience bangles unearthed, the excavator B.K.Shina opines that this monastery could be resided by nuns.

During the time of its inception, this site became more popular and the population of monastic establishment almost doubled which followed by a period of turmoil which witnessed the destruction of monastery twice during phases-III and IV. The destruction of the monastery of earlier phase may have been caused both by nature and by religious animosity. Being surrounded by the hill on the three sides the rainwater washed the structures. Attacks from outside may not be ruled out as the recovery of iron arrowheads and spearheads at the site, which must have been used to counter the onslaught. Gradually the monastery got damaged and abandoned and could not sustain further long and met its decline during 13th century A.D.

Conclusion

From study of Udaygiri archaeological site which was a famous and large Buddhist shrine continued its existence from 3rd century BCE to 13th Century AD it appears that the architecture of the shrines built in different periods abandoning the old ones had had intimate relationship with the doctrinal changes in Buddhist philosophy throughout these 1500 years. Changes in Buddhist philosophy influenced the Art and Culture along with architectural forms.

Appendix -I

Tabulated Form describing the details of all phases as discussed above

Phase – VI 100 years tentatively	Post Buddhist scenario (12th to 13th century A.D.).
Phase – V (300 years tentatively)	Rectangular shrine complex facing East (9th C. A.D. to 11th C. A.D.) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Worship of PadmapaniAvalokiteswara in standing position and other Bodhisattavs and 44 nos. images in different niches on the southern and weastern walls.• Worship of Akshyobha (Buddha in bhumisparsha mudra) with mandalas (diff. from of Bodhisattavas).• Worship of Padmapani with mandalas (different from of Bodhisattvas).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Worship of Akshyobha (Buddha in Bhumisparsha mudra) facing east in Monastery (Buddha in sanctum) (Udi- 1)
Phase – IV (200 years tentatively)	<p>Rectangular brick <i>chaitya-griha</i> with an entrance orienting North. (7th C. A.D. to 9th C. A.D.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Brick monastery with stone courtyard entrance towards – East (Udi-1).• Monastic seal (Udi – 1) <i>Madhavapura Mahavihara samagra Arya Bhikshu Sanghasya</i> was probably established separately by queens of Bhauma karas for nun to Practice. <i>Kalachakra Tantrans</i>.• Brick monastery double storied with stone courtyard entrance towards north (Udi-2).• <i>Dharanimantras</i> (god & goddess, temples, rituals, <i>stotras</i> (litanies) etc.• Worship of Akshyobha (Buddha in Bhumisparsha mudra) facing north in Monastery (Buddha in sanctum).• Worship of stone Stupa & <i>Pancha-dhyani</i> Buddha on lion pedestal in <i>chaitya-griha</i> facing North.• Seal Monastic (Udi-2)- <i>Simhaprastha Mahavihara Samagra Arya Bhikshu Sanghasya</i> (proto-devnagari) transformed from <i>Mahayana</i> to <i>Vajrayana</i> sectarian affiliation.• <i>Sankha-lipi</i> sealing the circular <i>chaitya</i> by the stone pavements of this period.
Phase - III (200 years tentatively)	<p>Rectangular brick <i>chaitya-griha</i> facing East (4th C. A.D. to 7th C. A.D.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Worship of Stupa (stone) with rectangular <i>brick-chaitya</i> facing east.• Probably Mahayana started image of Buddha kept in on alcove at brick-wall of rectangular brick <i>chaitya</i>.
Phase – II (400 years tentatively)	<p>Masonry apsidal <i>chaitya-griha</i> facing East- (1st C. B.C. to 3rd/4th C. A.D.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Brick Monastery with brick coryard & orientation its drain towards East.• Worship of Stupa with apsidal <i>chaitya</i>• Water Reservoir
Phase – I (200 years tentatively)	<p>Circular <i>chaitya</i> on stone platform facing North (3rd/2nd C. B.C. to 1st C. B.C.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Worship of Stupa with circular <i>chaitya</i> and other brick Stupas.

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Illustrations

(Fig-1) Plan and elevation of Gopika or Nagarjuni Cave.

Jivakamravana monastery at Rajgir

(Fig. 2) Location of Udayagiri

Rock-cut sculptures

Rock-cut and structural well

(Fig. 2) Plan of Udayagiri

(Pl. I) General view of stone platform.

(Pl. II) Circular *chaitya* on platform.

Lalitagiri chaitya

(Pl. III) Apsidal *chaitya* with its stupa.

(Pl. IV) Steps of apsidal *chaitya*.

Rock-cut apsidal *chaitya*, Bedsa.

(Pl. V) Elliptical impression on apsidal *chaitya*.

Plan of Udayagiri and Khandagiri.

(Pl. VI) Rectangular *chaitya* on apsidal platform.

(Pl. VII) Rectangular *chaitya* with lion pedestal

(Pl. VIII) Rectangular shrine complex.

(Pl. IX) Closed vaulted window

(Pl. X) Fragments of
Five *Dhyani* Buddhas

Fragment of eighteen handed Deity

(Pl. XI) Remains of late masonry structure.

